

THE IMPORTANCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE SKILLS IN CULTIVATING A GLOBAL ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS

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***Annotatsiya.** Hozirgi vaqtda ko'plab mamlakatlar ekologik muammolarga duch kelmoqda. Jahon hamjamiyati ekologik muammolarni hal qilish, jumladan, xalqaro axborot almashinuvi orqali sa'y-harakatlarini birlashtirmoqda. Shu munosabat bilan turli mamlakatlar vakillari o'rtasida yuqori sifatli muloqotni ta'minlash va ekologik mavzularda malakali tarjimoni ta'minlash zarurati tug'iladi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** ekologiya, atamalar tarjimasi, ekologik atamalar, atrof-muhitga oid tushuncha, ta'lim va ma'rifat.*

***Аннотация.** В настоящее время многие государства сталкиваются с экологическими трудностями. Мировое сообщество объединяет старания для решения экологических проблем, в том числе и при помощи международного обмена информацией. В связи с этим, возникает нужда в обеспечении качественной коммуникации между представителями разных стран и грамотном переводе по экологической тематике.*

***Ключевые слова:** экология, перевод терминов, экологические термины, экологическое сознание, образование и просвещение.*

***Abstract.** Currently, many countries are facing environmental problems. The world community joins efforts to solve environmental problems, including through international information exchange. In this regard, there is a need to ensure quality communication between representatives of different countries and competent translation on environmental topics.*

***Key words:** ecology, translation of terms, environmental terms, environmental awareness, education and enlightenment.*

Modern issues like climate change, biodiversity degradation, and pollution are impacted by international cooperation among countries and scientific communities. Such cooperation demands the integration of scientific resources, political determination, and social engagement on a global level. In relation to this, foreign languages, particularly English as a universal means of communication, have distinctive functions in the articulation of science, environmental politics, and diplomacy.

One of the main objectives of modern education is to develop a global approach to solving environmental problems. Foreign languages allow students and pupils to be part of an international community, to learn about best practices from other countries and to participate in global environmental initiatives. The theoretical basis for the study was the works of Maley A., Peachey N., Gunina N., Formenova D. A.

The relevance of the work is that environmental terms cause difficulties when translated into other languages. Ecology as a science continues to develop, new knowledge appears, and with it new vocabulary. It should be noted that dictionaries do not have time to record the emergence of new terms in environmental science.

As one can notice, ecology and other sciences combine terms. Let's consider how scientists define the word "term". According to A. A. Reformatsky, "terms are special words, limited by their special purpose, words that strive to be unambiguous as an exact expression of concepts and naming of things. This is necessary in science, technology, politics and diplomacy."

Environmental issues such as climate change, ocean pollution, and species extinction require coordinated efforts from around the world. Knowledge of foreign languages helps to integrate more easily into international environmental projects and research, allows scientists, environmentalists and activists to exchange experiences and develop effective strategies for sustainable development.

Primarily, the instance of knowing foreign languages is a gateway to information from other countries. Research suggests that more than one third of conservation related documents are published in foreign languages. Such publications are not utilized on a global scale which is a great loss of information and even wiser suggestions. This is especially so for countries with scarce linguistic resources.

English is the language in which the vast majority of scientific articles, monographs, and reports from international organizations like UNEP, IPCC, Greenpeace, and WWF are published.

English is the dominant language of communication for international environmental meetings such as the Conferences of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP). These conferences discuss broad climate policy issues, and the ability to communicate effectively in English is an asset for attendees. Without linguistic competence, it is impossible for a researcher to be able to readily navigate the modern scientific agenda, learn about environmental trends, and apply statistical and analytical materials. That is especially relevant in the case of rapidly evolving climate science, where data and counsel are regularly updated.

Second, knowledge of foreign languages is needed for international cooperation in science. Environmental problems have no boundaries, and their successful resolution is only possible through intensive communication between countries. Participation in international conferences, seminars, environmental forums means not only professional qualification, but also the ability to express one's ideas and hear others' ideas in foreign languages. In addition, the majority of interstate environmental projects involve collective research, publications and projects where language communication plays a key role.

It is also crucial to emphasize the role of foreign languages in eco-education and awareness. Current educational platforms (e.g., Coursera, edX, FutureLearn) offer immense diversity of sustainable development, climatology, English-language courses in ecology. All this broadens students' and professionals' scopes, making access to the globe's best training practices possible.

Selecting the appropriate content for English language courses is a serious task as most university students want to focus on their industry-related language rather than just study English. When introducing sustainability-related topics, course designers have to bear in mind that it is necessary to balance the students' needs and the relevant content. Another important consideration is the learning objectives, which have to be adjusted to make sure that they are formulated in the right manner and will help students to achieve the learning outcomes.

Finally, the knowledge of foreign languages contributes to world environmental awareness. Only through becoming aware of the magnitude and character of other countries' problems and learning from their experience is it possible to develop common solutions and good strategy. Language competence leads to understanding culture and world solidarity in protection of the environment.

Elsewhere, such as in Vanuatu's Tafea Province, local environmental knowledge transmitted through local languages is also of enormous use in agriculture and the wise management of natural resources. Loss of language has been found to lead to erosion of unique ecological practices, testifying to the importance of retaining linguistic and cultural diversity for sustainable development.

Knowledge of foreign languages helps to disseminate environmental ideas and values in an international context. Environmental education includes not only the study of theoretical aspects, but also the inculcation of environmental culture. Foreign languages encourage students to read books, articles, watch movies and participate in online courses in different languages, which broadens their understanding of environmental issues.

The growth of global environmental consciousness is a significant component of the role that foreign languages play in environmental education. Learning a foreign language helps one appreciate cultural differences and teaches one to consider the variety of solutions to environmental issues. It helps students develop a more nuanced and comprehensive view of the world, where everyone understands their role in protecting the environment on a global scale.

Studying foreign languages allows not only to master the skills of communication with people of different nationalities, but also contributes to the realization that environmental problems are not limited to one country, but are global. It develops a sense of universal responsibility and readiness to act for the benefit of all mankind.

Understanding environmental texts in a foreign language, as well as their translations, will be relevant for a long time, since knowledge about ecology and its problems continues to appear. Along with knowledge, new terms also appear. Translation of environmental terms is of particular interest to translators.

Thus, foreign languages, especially English, are an essential tool in studying and solving global environmental problems and an element of global environmental communication. They provide access to scientific information, facilitate international cooperation, promote scientific integration, knowledge dissemination, professional mobility and the formation of a common international agenda for sustainable development. To this end, language skills should be a priority in training environmental experts.

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